

Condensation of Glutaryl Chloride and Glutaric Anhydride with Phenols and Phenolic Ethers*

D. Chakravarti and Nripendra Kumar Roy

Glutaryl chloride has been condensed with phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresol, their methyl ethers, and resorcinol monomethyl ether in presence of aluminium chloride, forming exclusively γ -(*p*-hydroxy- or *p*-methoxybenzoyl)butyric acids with traces of diketones. But *p*-cresol, *p*-chlorophenol, and 2-chloro-5-hydroxytoluene provide aryloxy-esters under identical conditions. Phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresol and their methyl ethers, *p*-cresol, 2-chloro-5-hydroxytoluene, resorcinol, and its mono- and dimethyl ethers condense with glutaric anhydride, forming a mixture of *ortho*- and *para*-hydroxybenzoylbutyric acids and traces of diketones.

Glutaryl chloride has not been extensively used in the Friedel-Crafts reaction. From the reaction of glutaryl chloride with benzene, Auger¹ reported formation of $\alpha\gamma$ -dibenzoylpropane (I: R = R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H) as the main product with a small amount of γ -benzoylbutyric acid (II: R = R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H).

Plant and Tomlison² and Cason *et al.*³ have shown that glutaryl chloride exists in a lactone form (III). They obtained $\delta\delta$ -di-*p*-anisylvalerolactone (IV) and a diketone, $\alpha\gamma$ -dianisoylpropane (I: R₂ = OMe: R = R₁ = R₃ = H) when anisole was condensed with glutaryl chloride at a high temperature.

*Read at the Second Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society, held in Allahabad, December, 1964.

1. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1891, vi, 22, 358.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 856.

3. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 1675.

As no condensation with a free phenol appears to have been reported, the present authors have attempted the condensation of free phenols and its ethers with glutaryl chloride.

In the condensation of glutaryl chloride with the phenols, it has been observed that the acyl group in the keto-acids formed, always without exception, enters the *p*-position to the hydroxyl group, when the reaction is carried out at 0° in presence of nitrobenzene or tetrachloroethane as a solvent. This serves as an excellent method for the preparation of γ -(*p*-hydroxybenzoyl)butyric acids which have not been previously described in literature.

Phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresols, and their methyl ethers condense with glutaryl chloride, forming γ -(*p*-hydroxybenzoyl)butyric acids and traces of diketones in some cases. When the *p*-position of the OH group is occupied, instead of the keto-acid, an aryloxy-ester is the sole product of the reaction. Thus *p*-cresol, *p*-chlorophenol, and 2-chloro-5-hydroxy-toluene form exclusively the aryloxy-esters (V). Resorcinol monomethyl ether, however, provides exclusively diketones.

(V)

(VI)

In order to verify the identity of the compounds produced during condensation of glutaric anhydride with phenol, anisole, *o*- and *m*-cresols, their methyl ethers, resorcinol, and its mono- and dimethyl ethers, nitrobenzene or tetrachloroethane was used as a solvent in presence of aluminium chloride at low and high temperatures. At low temperatures (*ca.* 0-5°), no condensation took place, but at higher temperatures invariably good yields of *o*-hydroxybenzoylbutyric acids were obtained, sometimes along with traces of *p*-hydroxybenzoylbutyric acids.

The above keto-acids on the Clemmensen reduction under the usual conditions afforded the respective valeric acids, having the general formula (VI).

IR Spectra.—IR spectra of some of the compounds have been studied. It is interesting to note that *o*-hydroxybenzoylbutyric acid and bis-(*o*-hydroxyketones) show no absorption band in the region of 2.77—2.79 μ , characteristic of a free phenolic OH group⁴. All of the *o*-hydroxybenzoylbutyric acids, derived from glutaric anhydride, have a strong band in the region of 3.3-3.5 μ which may be attributed partly to the hydroxyl group, hydrogen-bonded to the *o*-carbonyl, and partly to the carbon-hydrogen stretching frequency. The carbonyl frequency in the case of *o*-hydroxybenzoylbutyric acid and bis-(*o*-hydroxyketones) is not also found at 5.96 μ , but shifted to 6.05-6.10 μ . But in the case of the *para*-analogues derived from glutaryl chloride, there are absorption bands at 2.75 μ and 5.95 μ , characteristic of free phenolic OH group and carbonyl frequency, respectively.

4. Thomas *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 5865.

The formation of *p*-hydroxybenzoylbutyric acid as the sole product of the reaction, without the formation of any trace of its *ortho*-isomer, may be ascribed to the bulkiness of the acetylating agent, viz., the acyl chloride-aluminium chloride complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

γ -(*p*-Hydroxybenzoyl)butyric Acid (II: $R_2=OH$; $R=R_1=R_3=H$).—A solution of freshly distilled phenol (2.4 g.) in nitrobenzene (20 ml) was cooled in a 250-ml, three-necked flask equipped with stirrer, dropping funnel, and a gas outlet tube. $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 7.5 g.) was added and the solution cooled to 0–5°. A solution of freshly distilled glutaryl chloride (4.2 g.) in nitrobenzene (5 ml) was added through the dropping funnel during 30 min. The reaction mixture was then kept at the room temperature for 18 hr. After decomposing it by ice and HCl, nitrobenzene was removed. The crude product, solidified on cooling, was then treated with Na_2CO_3 solution, filtered, and acidified when the hydroxyketo-acid separated. It was crystallised from hot water in colorless needles, m.p. 199–200°, yield 2 g., (Found: C, 63.16; H, 5.76. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.46; H, 5.85%). The hydroxy compound showed negative ferric reaction.

The 2,4-DNP, prepared in the usual way, was crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 14.65. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.43%).

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared by refluxing the hydroxyketo-acid with acetic anhydride and a few drops of pyridine for 6 hr. The product, isolated in the usual way, was crystallised from dilute ethanol in prismatic rods, m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 62.24; H, 5.48. $C_{13}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 62.40; H, 5.60%).

δ -(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)valeric acid was prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of γ -(*p*-hydroxybenzoyl)butyric acid. Zinc amalgam (10 g.) was added to a mixture of the hydroxyketo-acid (2 g.) in HCl (conc., 15 ml) and water (5 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 24 hr. The product, isolated in the usual way, was crystallised from hot water in colorless needles, m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 67.84; H, 7.10. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 68.04; H, 7.21%). The compounds prepared are listed in Table I.

Di-(*p*-chlorophenyl) glutarate (V: $R=Cl$; $R=H$) was prepared as in the above procedure by condensing *p*-chlorophenol (3.2 g.) with glutaryl chloride (4.3 g.) in presence of $AlCl_3$ (7.5 g.) at 0° in nitrobenzene as a solvent. The product isolated in the usual way was insoluble in Na_2CO_3 or NaOH solution. It was crystallised in prisms from ethanol, m.p. 120°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 57.58; H, 3.72. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4Cl_2$ requires C, 57.79; H, 3.96%).

A mixture of *p*-chlorophenol and glutaryl chloride, when heated on a water bath for 3 hr., furnished an ester, m.p. 120°; mixed m.p. with the compound, prepared as above, remained undepressed.

TABLE I
Condensation of phenols and phenolic ethers with glutaryl chloride.

Phenols and phenolic ethers.	Products formed.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	Derivatives.	Clemmensen reduction product.	Remarks.
1. Anisole (in nitrobenzene and tetrahydrofuran, 1:4)	(a) γ - <i>p</i> -Methoxybenzoyl)-butyric acid; m. p. 138° (dil. ethanol) (lit. 6 m. p. 138°).	[I: R ₁ =OMe; R ₂ =R ₃ =H]. C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄	C: 64.71% H: 6.18	64.86% 6.30	D. N. P., m. p. 145°; (Et Ac). [Found: N, 14.28. C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄ requires N, 14.56%].	Demethylated product m. p. 199°; mixed m. p. with γ -(<i>p</i> -hydroxybenzoyl) butyric acid, 199°.	
	(b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ ; 1,5-Bis-(4-methoxyphenyl)-pentane-dione; m. p. 101° (dil. ethanol) (lit. 5 m. p. 101°).	[I: R ₁ =OMe; R ₂ =R ₃ =H]. C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	C: 72.79 H: 6.21	73.07 6.41			
2. <i>o</i> -Cresol (in nitrobenzene)	(a) γ -(<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl)-butyric acid; m. p. 184° (hot water).	[II: R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OH; R ₃ =R ₃ =H]. C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	C: 64.61 H: 6.58	64.86 6.30	D. N. P., m. p. 180°; (Et OH) [Found: N, 13.68. C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄ requires N, 13.93%].	δ -(3-Methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)valeric acid [VI: R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OH; R ₃ =H]; m. p. 68° (hot water). [Found: C, 68.98; H, 7.42. C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ requires C, 69.23; H, 7.69%].	No colour with FeCl ₃ .
	(b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ ; 1,5-Bis-(3-methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-pentane-dione; m. p. 175°.	[I: R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OH; R ₃ =R ₃ =H]. C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	C: 72.97 H: 6.30	73.06 6.40	Oxime, m. p. 220° (Et OH). [Found: N, 7.92. C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂ requires N, 8.18%].	No colour with FeCl ₃ . This on methylation affords a product identical with the diketone obtained from <i>o</i> -cresol methyl ether and glutaryl chloride (mixed m. p. 130°).	
3. <i>o</i> -Cresol methyl ether (in tetrahydrofuran, 1:4)	(a) γ - <i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>m</i> -tolylbutyric acid; m. p. 140° (hot water) (lit. 6 m. p. 140°).	[II: R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OMe; R ₃ =R ₃ =H]. C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	C: 66.49 H: 6.78	66.50 6.82		Demethylated product m. p. 164°; mixed m. p. with γ -(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl) butyric acid, 184°.	
	(b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ ; 1,5-Bis-(3-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-pentane-dione; m. p. 130° (acetic acid).	[I: R ₁ =Me; R ₂ =OMe; R ₃ =R ₃ =H]. C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄	C: 73.94 H: 8.87	74.11 7.05			

CONDENSATION OF GLUTARYL CHLORIDE AND GLUTARIC ANHYDRIDE WITH PHENOLS

TABLE I (continued)

Phenols and phenolic ethers.	Products formed.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	Derivatives.	Clemmensen reduction products.	Remarks.
4. <i>m</i> -Cresol (in nitrobenzene)	(a) γ -(<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl)-butyric acid; m. p. 200° (hot water); $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$	[I: R=Me; R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =R ₃ =H] $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$	C : 64.68% H : 0.48	64.08% 6.30	D. N. P., m. p. 190° (EtOH-EtAc). [Found: N, 13.84. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 13.03%].	δ -(2-Methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) velorio acid [VI: R=Me; R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =R ₃ =H] m. p. 90° (hot water). [Found: C 69.07; H, 7.38. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C 69.23; H, 7.69%].	No colour with FeCl ₃
	(b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ : 1, 5-Bis-(2-methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)pentane-dione; m. p. 178° (acetic acid).	[I: R=Me; R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =R ₃ =H]. $C_{19}H_{20}O_4$	C : 72.85 H : 6.21	73.08 6.4	Oxime, m. p. 225° (dil. EtOH). [Found: N, 7.79. $C_{19}H_{24}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.18%].		No colour with FeCl ₃ . This on methylation provides a product, identical with the diketone obtained from <i>m</i> -cresol methyl ether and glutaryl chloride.
5. <i>m</i> -Cresol methyl ether (in tetrachloroethane)	(a) γ -(<i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl)-butyric acid; m. p. 120° (hot water) (lit ⁶ m. p. 138°). (b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ : 1, 5-Bis-(2-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)pentane-dione; b. p. 150°/0.2 mm.	[I: R=Me; R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H]. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ [I: R=Me; R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H]. $C_{21}H_{24}O_6$	C : 66.41 H : 6.74	66.56 6.82			Demethylated product m. p. 200°. Mixed m. p. with γ -(<i>p</i> -hydroxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl)-butyric acid, 200°.
6. Resorcinol monomethyl ether (in nitrobenzene)	1, 5-Bis-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl) pentane-dione; m. p. 130° (dil. EtOH).	[I: R=OH; R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H]. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$	C : 65.95 O : 5.64	66.27 5.81	Oxime, m. p. 100° (dil. EtOH). [Found: N, 7.14. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.48%].		Violet colour with FeCl ₃ . Oxidation to 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoic acid, m. p. 165° [mixed m. p. 165°].

6. Shah et al., *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1947, *Series A*, 15, No. 21, 1982.
N. B. Solvents of crystallisation are shown in parenthesis.

TABLE II
Condensation of phenols and phenolic ethers with glutaric anhydride.

Phenol and phenolic ethers.	Products formed.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	Derivatives.	Clemmensen reduction products.	Remarks.
1. Anisole (in tetra-chloro-ethane and nitrobenzene, 1:2). Temp. 0-5°.	(a) γ -(<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzoyl)-butyric acid; m. p. 138° (dil. EtOH) [lit. 6 m. p. 138°].	[II: R ₂ = OMe; R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H]. C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	C : 64.75% H : 6.21	64.86% 6.30	D. N. P., m. p. 145° (Et Ac). [Found: N, 14.31. C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₆ N ₄ requires N, 14.50%].	Demethylated product, m. p. 189°; mixed m. p. 199°.	
(b) <i>Inaccessible</i> in N ₂ O CO ₂ : 1,5-Bis-(4-methoxyphenyl)-pentane-dione; m. p. 101° (dil. EtOH) [lit. m. p. 101°]	[I: R ₂ = OMe; R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H]. C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	C : 72.70 H : 6.18	73.07 6.41				
2. <i>o</i> -Cresol (in tetra-chloro-ethane and nitrobenzene, 1:1). Temp. 120-30° for 3 hr.	(a) (<i>o</i> -Hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl)-butyric acid; m. p. 125° (hot water), yield 60%.	[II: R = OH; R ₁ = Me; R ₂ = R ₃ = H]. C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	C : 64.58 H : 6.21	64.80 6.30	D. N. P., m. p. 180° (EtOH). [Found: N, 13.82. C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 13.93%].	Violet colour with FeCl ₃ .	
(b) γ -(<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl)-butyric acid; m. p. 184° yield 40%.	[II: R ₁ = Me; R ₂ = OH; R = R ₃ = H].						Mixed m. p. 184°.
3. <i>o</i> -Cresol methyl ether (in tetra-chloro-ethane and nitrobenzene, 1:1). Temp. 0-5°.	γ -(<i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl) butyric acid; m. p. 140° (hot water), yield 75% [lit. 6 m. p. 140°].	[II: R ₁ = Me; R ₂ = OMe; R = R ₃ = H]. C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	C : 66.40 H : 6.72	66.56 6.82			Demethylated product m. p. 184°; mixed m. p. 184°.
4. <i>m</i> -Cresol (in tetra-chloroethane)	γ -(<i>o</i> -Hydroxy- <i>p</i> -tolyl) butyric acid; m. p. 140° (hot water), yield 80%.	[II: R = OH; R ₂ = Me; R ₁ = R ₃ = H]. C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	C : 66.10 H : 6.70	64.86 6.30	D. N. P., m. p. 200° (EtOH-benzene). [Found: N, 13.78. C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 13.93%].	δ -(2-Hydroxy-4-methylphenyl) valeric acid [VI: R = OH; R ₂ = Me; R ₁ = R ₃ = H]. m. p. 107° (hot water). [Found: C, 68.95; H, 7.58. C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ requires C, 69.23 H, 7.60%].	Violet colour with FeCl ₃ .

TABLE II (contd.)

Phenol and phenolic ethers.	Products formed.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	Derivatives.	Clemmensen reduction products.	Remarks.
6. <i>m</i> -Cresol methyl ether (in tetrahydroethane and nitrobenzene, 1:1), Temp. 0.5°.	γ -(<i>p</i> -Methoxy- <i>o</i> -tolyl) butyric acid, (70%); m.p. 120° (hot water) [lit. 5 m.p. 138°].	[I:R=Me; R ₂ =OMe; R ₃ =R ₁ =H] C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	C : 66.38% H : 6.78	66.56% 6.82			Demethylated product m.p. 200°; mixed m.p. 200°.
6. <i>p</i> -Cresol (in tetrahydroethane and nitrobenzene, 1:1), Temp. 50-60° for 2 hr. and 100° for ½ hr.	(a) γ -(2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzoyl)butyric acid; m.p. 95° (hot water). (b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ ; γ -(2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)dione; m.p. 140°; (EtOH) [lit., m.p. 142°]	[I:R=OH; R ₂ =Me; R ₁ =R ₃ =H]. C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₆	C : 64.78 H : 6.18	64.84 6.30	D.N.P. m.p. 150° (EtOH) [Found: N, 14.00. C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₄ requires N, 13.93%.] Oxime, m.p. 175° (dil. EtOH). [Found: N, 7.89. C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂ requires N, 8.18%]	δ -(2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl) valeric acid [VI: R=OH; R ₂ =Me; R ₁ =R ₃ =H]; b.p. 170°/2 mm. [Found: C, 68.92; H, 7.54. C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₅ requires C, 69.23, H, 7.69%].	Violet colour with FeCl ₃ .
7. 2-Chloro-5-hydroxybenzoic acid (tetrahydroethane and nitrobenzene, 1:1).	(a) γ -(2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chlorobenzoyl) butyric acid; m.p. 140° (dil. EtOH). (b) 1,5-Bis-(2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chlorophenyl)pentane dione; m.p. 160° (acetic acid).	[I:R=OH; R ₁ =H; R ₂ =Cl; R ₄ =Me] C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl	C : 55.82 H : 4.91	56.13 5.06	D.N.P. m.p. 210° (benzene). [Found: N, 11.65. C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₇ N ₄ Cl ₂ requires N, 11.88%]	δ -(2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chlorophenyl) valeric acid [VI: R=OH; R ₂ =Me; R ₃ =Cl; R ₁ =H]; m.p. 142° (dil. EtOH). [Found: C, 59.21; H, 5.92. C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₅ Cl requires C, 59.36; H, 6.16%].	(a) Violet colour with FeCl ₃ . (b) Violet colour with FeCl ₃ .

TABLE II (contd.)

Phenol and phenolic ether.	Products prepared.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	Derivatives.	Clemmensen reduction products.	Additional remark.
9. Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene). Temp. 10-15° for 2hr. and 30-32° for 2hr.	γ -(2,4-Dihydroxybenzoyl)-butyric acid (78%); m.p. 180° (dil EtOH).	[II:R=R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =R ₃ =H]. C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₅	C : 58.78% H : 5.21	58.92 5.35	D. N. P. m.p. 285° (dioxane).	δ -(2,4-Dihydroxy-phenyl)valeric acid [VI:R=R ₂ =OH;R ₁ R ₃ =H], b.p. 160°/1mm. [Found: C, 62.59; H, 6.24. C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ requires C, 62.85 H, 6.66%].	Violet colour with FeCl ₃ .
9. Resorcinol monomethyl ether (in nitrobenzene). Temp. 10-15° for 2 and 30° for 1 hr.	(a) γ -(2-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoyl) butyric acid, m.p. 159° (dil. ethanol) (lit ⁶ , m.p. 175° (75%).	[II:R=OH;R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H] C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₅	C : 60.31 H : 5.49	60.50 5.88	D. N. P. m.p. 138° (EtOH). [Found: N, 13.12, C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄ requires N, 13.3%].	δ -(2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl) valeric acid [VI: R=OH; R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H], m.p. 125° (hot water). [Found: C, 63.95; H, 6.92. C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ requires C, 64.28; H, 7.14%].	Violet colour with FeCl ₃ .
	(b) Insoluble in Na ₂ CO ₃ ; 1,5-Bis-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl) pentane-dione; m.p. 130°.	[I:R=OH;R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H] C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₆	C : 66.01 H : 5.72	66.27 5.81			Mixed m. p. 130°; violet colour with FeCl ₃ .
10. Resorcinol dimethyl ether (in nitrobenzene). Temp. -5.0° for 2 hr.	γ -(2,4-Dihydroxybenzyl) butyric acid, m.p. 110° (dil. EtOH) [lit ⁶ , m.p. 100°] (80%).	(II: R=R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H). C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₅	C : 61.68 H : 6.62	61.90 6.34			Violet colour with FeCl ₃ . Oxidation product dimethoxy- β -resorcylic acid; m.p. 107°; mixed m.p. 107°.

N.B. Figures in the second column parentheses denote yields; solvents of crystallisation are shown in parentheses.

CONDENSATION OF GLUTARYL CHLORIDE AND GLUTARIC ANHYDRIDE WITH PHENOLS

Di-(p-tolyl) glutarate (V: R=Me; R₁=H) was prepared by the above procedure and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 95° (lit.* m.p. 86°), yield 80%. (Found: C, 72.98; H, 6.25. Calc. for C₁₉H₂₀O₄: C, 73.07; H, 6.41%).

Di-3-methyl-4-chlorophenyl glutarate (V: R=OMe; R₁=Cl) was prepared similarly as above. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 68°, yield 80%. (Found: C, 59.74; H, 4.58. C₁₉H₁₈O₄Cl₂ requires C, 59.84; H, 4.72%).

2-Chloro-5-hydroxytoluene and glutaryl chloride, on refluxing on a water bath for 3 hr., provided an ester, m.p. 68°; mixed m.p. with the compound prepared as above remained undepressed.

γ-(o-Hydroxybenzoyl)butyric Acid (II: R=OH; R₁=R₂=R₃=H).—To a solution of freshly distilled phenol (2 g.) in tetrachloroethane (15 ml) and nitrobenzene (15 ml), cooled in a 250-ml, three-necked flask equipped with stirrer, condenser, and a gas outlet tube, glutaric anhydride (2 g.) was added. AlCl₃ (5 g.) was added gradually to the reaction mixture. After the initial reaction had ceased, the mixture was heated in an oil bath at 130-40° for 3 hr. It was then decomposed with ice and HCl and the solvent removed with steam. The crude acid and the solvent were removed with steam. The crude acid, obtained after cooling, was extracted with Na₂CO₃ solution and acidified. The product was a mixture of *ortho*- and *para*-isomers.

The *ortho*-isomer was separated by fractional crystallisation from hot water as needles, m.p. 100° and *para* isomer melted at 199° (mixed m.p. with the earlier sample, 199°); yields of *o*- and *p*-isomers were 50% each. (Found: C, 63.20; H, 5.78. C₁₁H₁₂O₄ requires C, 63.46, H, 5.85%). It developed a violet colour with FeCl₃.

2,4-DNP, prepared in the usual way, was crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and ethyl acetate as red prisms, m.p. 185°. (Found: N, 14.21. C₁₇H₁₆O₇N₄ requires N, 14.43%). The compounds prepared are listed in Table II.